

Milestone: MS32 - Privacy-enhancing solutions

Lead Participant: IMEC

Author: Wilfried Verachtert

Due: 30th April 2025

Date Of Completion: 7th November 2025

Means of Verification

Deliverable D8.6 Report on privacy enhancing solutions: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17579905>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Initial version: No

Final Version: Yes
because of misunderstanding about the review process.

Project participants & others

Imec (Belgium)

Next action steps

None

